

RESEARCH OF THE STATE OF HEALTH OF SCHOOLCHILDREN IN THE CITY OF SAMARKAND ACCORDING TO THE DATA OF PREVENTIVE EXAMINATIONS

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SUMMARY. The health of children and adolescents in any society and in any socio-economic and political situations is an urgent problem and a matter of priority, as it determines the future of the country, the gene pool of the nation, the scientific and economic potential of society and, along with other demographic indicators, is a sensitive barometer socio-economic development of the country. The health of schoolchildren is one of the priority areas of the state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1]. However, dynamic monitoring of the health status of the child population, especially schoolchildren, reveals a persistent trend of deterioration in health indicators; the proportion of healthy schoolchildren decreases with a simultaneous increase in chronic forms of diseases when moving from class to class in the learning process, the health index decreases[2].

KEYWORDS: schoolchildren, preventive examinations, health groups.

The purpose of the study is to study the ratio of health groups and the structure of the pathology of schoolchildren in Samarkand.

Materials and methods. Analysis of preventive examination maps at pediatric sites of 53 and 54 family polyclinics in Samarkand.

Results and its discussion. In the course of the study, preventive examination cards of 256 children were analyzed. The groups were formed according to the age principle and corresponded to the decreed terms for in-depth preventive medical examinations. The group of children aged 7-8 years was 33%, 10-13 years old - 29%, 15-17 years old - 38%. 22% of children were registered at the dispensary. Analysis

of the distribution by health groups showed: group I was 22.3%, II - 49.1%, III - 27.6%, IV - 1.1%. Considering the obtained data in terms of age, it was revealed that the indicators in the age groups of children 7–8 years old and 10–13 years old were comparable (group I - 26.5 and 25.8%, group II - 49.5 and 45.1%, III - 24 and 26.8%, respectively). The studied indicators were excellent in the group of children aged 15–17 years. Among the children of this group, the ratio of health groups looked as follows: group I - 11.6%, group II - 53.2%, group III - 33.7%. In all age groups in the structure of pathology, the following diseases have the largest share: diseases of the musculoskeletal system - 28.57%, of the organ of vision - 17.14% and ENT organs - 12%. Diseases of the respiratory organs (10.12%), nervous (9.61%), urinary (8.83%), endocrine (7.01%), cardiovascular (3.37%) systems, gastrointestinal tract (2.87%) were presented in this ratio.

Findings. The distribution by health groups showed comparable results in children aged 7–8 and 10–12 years old. Whereas in the group of 15-17-year-olds, the number of healthy children decreases by 2 times in comparison with younger schoolchildren and the number of students of health groups II and III increases - more than a third have chronic pathology and 53.2% - various functional deviations. The diseases of the musculoskeletal system, the organ of vision and the ENT organs are predominant in the structure of childhood diseases.

List of used literature

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the protection of the health of citizens”. – 1996
2. Khudayarov A.A., Mutalova Z.D., Magdaliev O.D. // Public health and health care in the Republic of Uzbekistan // Information statistical collections // MZ RUZ. - Tashkent, 2004 - 2020.